

A sensitive and selective extractive spectrophotometric determination of tungsten(VI) using 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran

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Abstract : A simple, rapid, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of tungsten(VI) in trace amounts is developed using 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (CHMPB) as a reagent for the complexation of metal ion and extracting the 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex into dichloromethane from 0.2 M HCl solution. It obeys Beer's law in the range 0–2.1 $\mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ with molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity at 415 nm as $6.08 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.00302 \mu\text{g W cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The method is free from the interference of a large number of elements (40) and has been applied for the determination of tungsten in a variety of samples with satisfactory accuracy.

Keywords : Spectrophotometric determination, selective extraction, tungsten(VI) determination.

The existing spectrophotometric methods of determination of tungsten in trace amounts using vanadophosphoric acid¹, thiocyanate¹, dithiol¹ and quinaldic acid² suffer from low sensitivity, complexity in procedures and non-selectivity and are time consuming. This has warranted to search for new better methods which are simpler, more sensitive, selective and rapid. Accordingly, 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (CHMPB) has been used as a complexing agent for tungsten(VI) in the spectrophotometric determination of the metal ion to meet the above requirements.

Results and discussion

Effect of nature of acids on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex : The absorbance of the W^{VI} -CHMPB complex in dichloromethane was greatly influenced by the nature of the acids. From 0.2 M acidity fixed in each case, the absorbance was found to decrease in the order : HCl (0.330) > HClO_4 (0.325) > H_2SO_4 (0.315) > H_3PO_4 (0.240) > CH_3COOH (0.170). Therefore, HCl medium was preferred for further studies.

Effect of organic solvents on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex : Various organic solvents namely dichloromethane, chloroform, benzene, 1,2-dichloroethane, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, isobutyl methyl ketone, ethyl acetate, isoamyl acetate, cyclohex-

ane and isoamyl alcohol extracted the metal complex in the decreasing order of absorbance. As dichloromethane gave maximum absorbance with a rapid and clear phase separation, it was chosen as the most suitable extractant. A single equilibration of the aqueous phase with equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane under optimum conditions gave quantitative (100%) recovery of W^{VI} -CHMPB complex. The complete absence of tungsten in the raffinate was tested by the more sensitive 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran method³.

λ_{max} and stability of the complex : The absorption spectrum of the complex indicated that the maximum lied at 410–417 nm in the visible region, where the reagent blank also showed some absorbance (Fig. 1). In dichloromethane, the absorbance remained unchanged for more than 2 h.

Effect of concentration of HCl, CHMPB and equilibration time on the absorbance of the complex : The optimum values of above parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 0.12–0.30 M HCl, 0.6–2.1 ml of 0.1% CHMPB (in acetone) and 5–240 s equilibration time for $\leq 21 \mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}}$ per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1). Also the order of addition of the reagent and HCl should be kept throughout the same as per proposed procedure as on changing this order low absorbance is observed.

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of the W-complex

HCl (M) ^a	0.02	0.06	0.10	0.12-0.30	0.32	0.36	0.40
Absorbance	0.220	0.280	0.320	0.330	0.320	0.295	0.270
0.1% CHMPB (ml) ^b	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.6-2.1	2.2	2.3	2.5
Absorbance	0.200	0.250	0.290	0.330	0.320	0.305	0.270
Equilibration time (s) ^c	0	2	5-240				
Absorbance	0.050	0.180	0.330				

^aW^{VI} = 10 µg. HCl = variable, 0.1% CHMPB = 1 ml, equilibration time = 30 s, solvent = dichloromethane; ^bHCl = 0.2 M, other conditions being the same as in (a) except for the variation in CHMPB concentration, also ^bCHMPB = 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran; ^c0.1% (w/v) CHMPB in acetone = 1 ml, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of W^{VI}-CHMPB complex in dichloromethane: Curve A - Complex against reagent blank, Curve B - Reagent blank against pure dichloromethane. 2 µg W ml⁻¹ CHMPB (0.1%) = 1 ml, HCl = 0.2 M.

Fig. 2. Job's method of continuous variations. Total concentration [W] + [CHMPB] = 5.43 × 10⁻⁴ M: Curve A - 415 nm, Curve B - 435 nm, HCl = 0.2 M.

Beer's law range, molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and composition of the complex: Beer's law was valid in the concentration range of 0-2.1 µg ml⁻¹ W^{VI}. However, the optimum range for the determination of tungsten, as evaluated from a Ringbom plot⁴, was calculated to be 0.42-2.09 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 415 nm were 6.08 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.00302 µg W cm⁻², respectively. The ratio of W^{VI} and CHMPB in the extracted species was determined as 1 : 2 by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁵ for a two phase system (Fig. 2). This was further confirmed by the mole ratio (Fig. 3) and equilibrium shift⁶ (Fig. 4) methods.

Effect of diverse ions: Under the optimum conditions of the procedure in 10 ml aqueous volume (mg amounts in parentheses), chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulfate, carbonate, thiourea and sulfite (100 each); ascorbic acid, dithionite, sulfosalicylic acid and phosphate (70 each); thiocyanate, acetate and hydrazine sulfate (50 each);

Fig. 3. Mole ratio method. Total concentration of metal fixed, [W] = 5.43 × 10⁻⁴ M: Curve A - 415 nm, Curve B - 435 nm, HCl = 0.2 M.

'disodium' EDTA (40); tartrate (7); citrate (5); fluoride (0.5); glycerol (0.5 ml) and H₂O₂ (6% w/v) (0.3 ml) were without effect. However, oxalate even in traces interfered seriously. Among the cations, Ca^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Al^{III}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Hg^{II} and As^V (10 each); Ni^{II} and Pb^{II} (9 each); Bi^{III} (8); Cd^{II}, Ag^I, Sb^{III} and Be^{II} (5 each); U^{VI} and Cr^{III,VI} (4 each); Se^{IV} and Os^{VIII} (3 each);

Fig. 4. Equilibrium shift method showing a plot of $\log [A_1/(A_0-A_1)]$ vs $\log C_L$. A_1 = absorbance at a reagent concentration C_L , A_0 = absorbance at complete formation of the complex and C_L = total concentration of the reagent added. Conditions : Concn. of W^{VI} = $5.43 \times 10^{-4} M$; concn. of CHMPB = 1.086×10^{-4} – $14.661 \times 10^{-4} M$; 0.2 M HCl; aqueous volume = solvent volume = 10 ml; solvent = dichloromethane; λ_{max} = 415 nm; number of extractions = 1. CHMPB = 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran.

Cu^{II} (2); Ce^{IV} , La^{III} and Th^{IV} (1 each); Pt^{IV} (0.5); Re^{VII} (0.4); Zr^{IV} , Ir^{III} , Au^{III} , Nb^V and Ta^V (0.1 each); Ru^{III} (0.08); Fe^{III} (0.05) and Pd^{II} (0.04) caused < 1% error in absorbance. Sn^{II} , Ti^{IV} , V^V and Mo^{VI} did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure.

The wide applicability of the method was tested by carrying out the analysis of various synthetic and technical samples with satisfactory results ($\sigma = \pm 17 \times 10^{-4}$).

(CHMPB)

Experimental

A Shimadzu 140-02 (UV-VIS) spectrophotometer with

10 mm matched glass cells was used for routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies. Solutions of W^{VI} , other ions and hydrochloric acid were prepared as reported earlier⁷. 6-Chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (CHMPB), m.p. 193–195°, was synthesized by the literature method⁸ and dissolved in acetone to give 0.1% (w/v) solution. The chemical formula of the compound is $C_{16}H_{11}O_4Cl$ and its structure is

Dichloromethane(Ranbaxy) was used as such.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing a known volume of tungsten(VI) solution with solutions of other metal ions in suitable proportions. Reverberatory flue dust sample was brought into solution as reported³ and tungsten determined in the aliquots (0.5 and 1.5 ml) by the proposed method.

Procedure : To the sample solution containing $\leq 21 \mu g$ tungsten(VI) and other ions taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel were added 2 M hydrochloric acid (1 ml), 0.1% (w/v) CHMPB (1 ml) and sufficient deionized water to make up the volume to 10 ml. It was then equilibrated once with an equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane for 30 s. The light yellow organic phase after separation, was poured over anhydrous sodium sulfate for removal of any retained water. The absorbance of the complex in the extract was measured at 415 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank and the amount of tungsten was determined from the standard curve prepared in an analogous manner.

For 0.1 mg Sn^{II} was added 40 mg 'disodium' EDTA, for each of 0.05 mg V^V and Mo^{VI} was added 0.3 ml of 6% (w/v) H_2O_2 and for 0.5 mg Ti^{IV} was added 50 mg sodium phosphate, as masking agents, prior to the addition of CHMPB in 10 ml aqueous volume.

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